

PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES OF THE CENTRAL KALIMANTAN REGIONAL POLICE AGAINST NARCOTICS DISTRIBUTION AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN ACCORDANCE WITH LAW NO. 35 OF 2009 ON NARCOTICS

Jenika^{1*}, Aristoteles², Andika Wijaya³

^{1,2,3}Universitas Palangka Raya, Palangka Raya

E-mail: jenikajennn12@gmail.com, aristoteles@law.upr.ac.id, andikawijaya@law.upr.ac.id

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Abstract

The abuse and distribution of narcotics among university students remains a growing concern, particularly in Central Kalimantan. This study aims to analyze the Upayaes and approaches implemented by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) in preventing drug circulation within academic environments, especially in reference to the enforcement of Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics. Utilizing a juridical-empirical method, data were collected through interviews, field observations, and literature studies. The findings reveal that the police have initiated several preventive measures including public campaigns, educational outreach, utilization of social media platforms, and formal collaborations with universities through the formation of Anti-Narcotics Task Forces. However, these initiatives, especially those focused directly on students, remain inconsistent and often event-based. Legal enforcement has been applied equally, with no exemption for students, while still allowing for rehabilitation alternatives for non-distributing users. The main challenges faced include limited funding, low student participation, weak family reporting, and inadequate intersectoral coordination. This study recommends enhancing structured and continuous drug prevention programs on campus, strengthening institutional support from universities and student organizations, and increasing family involvement in early detection and intervention. The outcomes of this research are expected to support the development of more effective anti-narcotics policies within higher education institutions and to promote a more vigilant and resilient campus culture against drug abuse.

Keywords: *Narcotics, Students, Prevention.*

INTRODUCTION

Narcotics-related crimes are a form of offense that continue to pose a serious threat to social stability and public health in various regions, including in the city of Palangka Raya. In recent years, cases of narcotics abuse and trafficking in this region have shown an alarming upward trend. Based on data from the Palangka Raya District Court, in 2024 alone, a total of 137 narcotics cases were processed, making it the most dominant type of criminal offense compared to other crimes. This condition indicates that the narcotics issue is no longer a peripheral matter, but has become a major concern within the local legal and social order system. One of the groups that has come under increasing attention in the context of narcotics abuse is university students. As part of the young generation in a transitional phase toward adulthood, students often become easy targets for drug distribution networks. The modes of distribution have also become increasingly varied, ranging from approaches through daily social interactions and drug parties to the use of illegal substances for enhancing stamina or academic focus. This illustrates that the campus environment, which should serve as a place for intellectual development, has instead become vulnerable to being exploited as a ground for narcotics distribution. In fact, normatively, Indonesia already has fairly strict regulations through Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. However, the implementation of these regulations has not been fully effective in addressing narcotics abuse, particularly among university students. Several factors contributing to the weak control over narcotics include low student awareness of the dangers of drugs, inadequate supervision of drug distribution within campus environments, and the lack of preventive and educational interventions. This phenomenon reflects a gap between the existing regulations and the reality in the field. A study conducted on 250 students from nine faculties at the University of Palangka Raya revealed that the role of religious education serves as both a preventive and rehabilitative means. Preventive

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education is carried out through exemplary behavior, counseling, and instilling a foundation of faith. The rehabilitative aspect is implemented by providing guidance to students who are involved in narcotics abuse. However, several cases of narcotics abuse and trafficking involving university students in Palangka Raya still occur frequently. This abuse is caused by various factors, primarily social environmental pressure, weak self-control, and a lack of understanding of the harmful effects of narcotics. The students involved are generally young, in a stage of self-discovery, and tend to be easily influenced by unhealthy social interactions. The abuse is not limited to experimental use but has developed into addiction, which disrupts their academic and social activities. Some have even become involved in narcotics distribution networks, lured by the promise of quick financial gain. In 2024, a female student from one of the universities in Palangka Raya was caught red-handed distributing and possessing a package of marijuana weighing 910 grams. In the same year, the Central Kalimantan Regional Police arrested three individuals who were found in possession of 36 packets of methamphetamine weighing 17.42 grams at a house, one of whom was a university student. In 2023, a university student in Palangka Raya was caught ordering narcotics online—specifically 108.49 grams of marijuana worth Rp 1.5 million—which was shipped via a long-distance delivery service from Medan, North Sumatra. These data clearly indicate that over the past two years, there have still been cases related to narcotics involving university students. Most recently, in 2025, a 37-year-old man identified by the initials H, who worked as a daily laborer, was arrested by the Narcotics Investigation Unit of the Kotawaringin Timur (Kotim) Police for his involvement in methamphetamine trafficking. The arrest took place on Wednesday, September 24, 2025, at a boarding house on Jalan Revolusi, Ketapang Sub-district, Mentawa Baru Ketapang, Sampit. During the raid, police found 30 packets of methamphetamine ready for distribution, with a total weight of approximately 7 grams, hidden by the suspect in his residence. Based on the investigation, the suspect was known to frequently distribute drugs in the area. The evidence and the suspect have been secured at the Kotim Police Headquarters for further legal proceedings. The suspect has been charged under Article 114(1) in conjunction with Article 112(1) of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, carrying a minimum sentence of four years’ imprisonment. This case adds to the growing list of narcotics distribution cases uncovered in Kotim, an area known for its high vulnerability to the circulation of illicit drugs.

Table 1. Suspect Classification of Narcotics Crime (TP) from 2020 to 2025

YEAR	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
CASE	628	642	373	647	645	388
SUSPECT	757	761	468	776	786	472
GENDER						
MAN	694	675	775	703	682	425
WOMAN	63	86	85	73	104	47
AGE						
< 15	0	0	1	0	1	0
15-16	4	5	41	2	7	8
18-25	116	84	99	106	113	62
26-30	150	151	137	129	149	82
31-40	281	305	310	295	275	176
41-50	172	180	220	197	191	117
> 51	34	36	50	47	50	27
EDUCATION BACKGROUND						
NON EDUCATION	5	0	5	4	3	2
SD/ SEDERAJAT	172	175	48	172	155	102
SMP/ SEDERAJAT	205	228	124	225	195	121
SMA/ SEDERAJAT	353	336	268	359	413	232
PT (D3/S1/S2)	22	22	23	16	20	15
PROFESSION						
STUDENT	17	14	5	5	3	6

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UNIVERSITY STUDENT	8	18	7	8	9	9
SWASTA	386	292	192	272	256	125
WIRASWASTA	136	188	112	193	199	119
Laborer/ Merchant	60	73	37	64	48	46
Farmer/Fisherman	50	58	40	82	71	55
Police/Soldier (TNI)	4	1	2	0	4	1
Civil servants/Honoror	22	13	4	11	14	8
OJEK/ Driver	16	21	17	23	26	8
Housewife	31	58	27	56	72	30
Unemployment	27	25	25	61	80	63
Prisoner	0	0	0	1	4	2

Based on the results of interviews and document analysis at the Narcotics Investigation Directorate of the Central Kalimantan Regional Police, the classification data of narcotics crime suspects in Central Kalimantan, as shown in the table above for the 2020 to 2025 period, demonstrate diverse dynamics based on gender, age, education, and occupation. The number of cases each year tends to fluctuate. For instance, in 2020 there were 628 cases with 757 suspects, which increased to 647 cases in 2023 with 776 suspects, then sharply declined in 2024 and 2025 to 389 and 388 cases with 786 and 472 suspects, respectively. In terms of gender, males consistently dominate the number of suspects, reaching the highest figure in 2024 with 682 individuals, while females account for a much smaller proportion, with the highest number being 104 in the same year. Based on age groups, most suspects fall within the productive age ranges of 26 to 30 and 31 to 40 years, with each group recording hundreds of suspects annually. This indicates that young and middle-aged adults are the most vulnerable to involvement in narcotics-related cases. From an educational standpoint, the majority of suspects have a junior or senior high school education (SMP and SMA or equivalent), with the highest numbers recorded in 2020, 205 from junior high school and 338 from senior high school, showing that individuals with secondary education levels make up the dominant group.

From the employment perspective, the majority of suspects come from the private and self-employed sectors, with the highest numbers recorded in 2020, reaching 386 individuals from the private sector and 186 from the self-employed. Other notable categories include laborers/traders, farmers/fishermen, and the unemployed, whose figures remain relatively stable each year. Meanwhile, the number of suspects among students and university students is not as high as those in other occupational categories, yet it still shows a concerning trend. Records indicate that student suspects reached 17 individuals in 2020, while university students peaked at 18 individuals in 2021. Although the number of university students involved later tended to remain stable from 2023 to 2025, ranging between 8 and 9 individuals, this issue still deserves serious attention. As members of the intellectual community, university students should be at the forefront of advocating against drug abuse. However, the fact that some still fall into involvement indicates that preventive and supervisory measures within higher education institutions need to be strengthened.

Although a group of students in Palangka Raya has shown genuine concern over the rise of drug abuse among their peers by actively participating in the Peer Tutor Program, they use creative approaches such as drawing activities and open discussions to not only provide an understanding of the dangers of drugs but also to foster participants' self-awareness about the importance of social support, life purpose, and a healthy social environment. Students of the University of Palangka Raya have also taken active roles in addressing the potential for drug abuse among school students through a Community Service Program (KKN) conducted at SD Negeri Rodok. In this program, they held a socialization activity themed "The Dangers of Smoking and Its Relationship with Narcotics," targeting fourth to sixth grade students. The session not only discussed the harmful effects of smoking on children's health but also explained that nicotine addiction can serve as an initial gateway to narcotics abuse. The police, as one of the law enforcement institutions, play an important role in both the prevention and handling of drug-related cases, including those involving students and university students. In 2025, the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) launched the #GenerasiAntiNarkoba campaign targeting students

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and university students across Central Kalimantan. This initiative represents one of the law enforcement efforts to remind the young generation in the region to stay away from drugs.

Image 1.1 The #GenerasiAntiNarkoba campaign by the Multimedia Team of the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (Polda Kalteng) in 2025.

In reality, as stated by the Regional Secretary of Central Kalimantan in 2024 during the Coordination Meeting on the Development and Guidance of Drug-Threat-Resilient Regencies/Cities, efforts to prevent drug use among university students still face several challenges. Some of the obstacles encountered in implementing these preventive measures include limited human resources and budget on the part of the police, weak cross-sectoral coordination, and a lack of support from the academic community itself. With this background, the present study aims to conduct an in-depth analysis of the efforts implemented by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) to prevent narcotics distribution among university students in Palangka Raya. This study also seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of the preventive approaches that have been carried out and to identify various obstacles that hinder their implementation. The findings of this research are expected to provide relevant recommendations for enhancing narcotics prevention efforts within higher education institutions, as well as to serve as input for broader narcotics control policies.

METHOD

This study employs an empirical juridical method, which examines the law not only from the perspective of legislation but also from its practical implementation in the field. The juridical approach is used to analyze Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, which serves as the legal basis for narcotics prevention efforts by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng). Meanwhile, the empirical approach is applied to understand how these regulations are implemented by law enforcement officers in addressing narcotics issues within the student environment. Data were collected through document studies and interviews with relevant parties, such as members of POLDA Kalteng. This research is descriptive qualitative in nature, providing an in-depth overview of the efforts and challenges faced by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) in preventing narcotics distribution among university students. Data collection techniques include interviews and literature review. Interviews were conducted with parties directly involved in narcotics prevention, while the literature review was used to explore relevant legal references. The collected data were then analyzed narratively to identify patterns and gain insights into the policies implemented by the police. This technique enables the study to offer broader insights into the effectiveness of narcotics prevention policies among university students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on an interview with AIPTU Warsito from the Narcotics Directorate of the Central Kalimantan Regional Police, efforts to prevent drug abuse among university students are carried out through socialization activities, counseling sessions, and educational campaigns conducted in schools, universities, and public spaces, including through social media platforms. The Central Kalimantan Police (Polda Kalteng) also collaborate with higher education institutions by establishing Campus Anti-Narcotics Task Forces and organizing joint seminars to enhance legal awareness and understanding of the dangers of drugs. However, the effectiveness of these programs remains constrained by limited funding, low student participation, and suboptimal coordination among universities,

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families, and law enforcement agencies. Nevertheless, the ongoing collaborative efforts and educational approaches demonstrate Polda Kalteng's strong commitment to fostering a drug-aware and drug-free academic environment.

Efforts and Programs for Narcotics Prevention by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng)

Based on an interview with AIPTU Warsito, Acting Head of Evaluation Section, Subdivision of Operational Guidance, Narcotics Directorate, Central Kalimantan Regional Police (Polda Kalteng). , The Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) have implemented various preventive measures to combat narcotics distribution, particularly among university students. These efforts are generally carried out for the wider community, although some are specifically directed toward campus environments. The common forms of prevention include educational activities presented in various formats such as public lectures, counseling sessions, socialization programs, and public awareness campaigns.

Socialization activities related to narcotics for university students are often carried out alongside community and student events. In May 2025, the Narcotics Directorate of the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (Ditresnarkoba Polda Kalteng) conducted socialization, counseling, and sticker distribution activities about the dangers of drug abuse at several locations in Palangka Raya City, such as the Kahayan Bridge Culinary Tourism Area, several schools and universities, and even among the Punk community of Palangka Raya. In August 2025, the Central Kalimantan Police Chief, Inspector General Iwan Kurniawan, served as a guest speaker at the Academic and Student Culture Orientation (PBAK) event at UIN Palangka Raya, where he shared information on narcotics abuse among students. In the same month and year, POLDA Kalteng, in collaboration with the Provincial Government of Central Kalimantan and Governor H. Agustiar, officially opened the 2025 Student Orientation Program (PKKMB) at the University of Palangka Raya (UPR). On that occasion, the Police Chief also delivered a message emphasizing the importance of preventing drug use and guiding students on how to avoid involvement in such activities.

This campaign was carried out through the installation of banners, the distribution of stickers, and the direct delivery of messages by police personnel to individuals or groups. For university students, such activities are often integrated into academic forums or student organization events. Through this approach, the police aim to engage with students more closely and continuously. In its implementation, the outreach and socialization programs conducted by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) are often carried out during specific moments considered effective, such as new student admissions or campus orientation activities. In these programs, police officers are invited to deliver materials on the dangers of narcotics, types of illegal substances, and the legal consequences for users and distributors. These activities, known as PKKMB (Campus Life Introduction Program for New Students), serve as an efficient channel for instilling early awareness among new students about the consequences of drug involvement. The outreach efforts are not limited to students but also involve lecturers and other academic staff through joint seminars or discussion forums within higher education institutions.

The identification of campuses or areas considered vulnerable to narcotics abuse is carried out based on an analysis of suspect data collected over a certain period. The police record the suspects' place of residence, employment status, and connection to educational institutions. If a suspect is found to still hold student status, this information is further traced to determine the university of origin and estimate its level of vulnerability. Although not all of this data is made publicly available, the process helps the Regional Police (POLDA) establish priority scales for preventive interventions at specific universities. This mapping serves as a reference for the police in selecting locations and target groups for subsequent educational programs. The Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) has also established cooperation with universities through various forms, both formal and non-formal. One example of such collaboration is the involvement of student executive bodies (BEM) in organizing seminars or awareness programs. In addition, there is also a program for the establishment of Campus Anti-Narcotics Task Forces, which serves as a follow-up to Presidential Instruction No. 2 of 2020. This task force involves lecturers, students, and representatives from POLDA, who are responsible for providing legal guidance and supervision. In one instance, POLDA personnel participated as members of the task force at the University of Palangka Raya, coordinating directly with faculty representatives and campus leaders appointed to drive the initiative. This collaboration demonstrates efforts to create an internal system within the campus environment that is more responsive to issues related to narcotics distribution.

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In terms of communication and information dissemination, the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) also utilizes social media as a digital campaign platform. The official police accounts on various platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok are used to deliver educational messages, encourage people to stay away from drugs, and share information about ongoing or completed activities. The materials shared include short videos, infographics, and field documentation, such as drug busts and awareness programs. Although not specifically targeted at university students, this content is expected to reach young people who are active on digital platforms. Through this approach, prevention messages are expected to be received in a more engaging and easily understandable way. Although various efforts have been made, programs specifically and continuously targeted at university students are not yet fully available. Most prevention activities are general in nature and cover various community groups, including students and university students. However, in several agendas, university students remain one of the target segments. For instance, in the prevention program scheduled for July, the police plan to conduct an awareness session at one of the universities. This indicates that although there is not yet a consistently dedicated program for university students, there remains both the intention and opportunity to make them the focus of future activities. An adaptive approach to campus dynamics is part of the effort to continue reaching this group in a contextually relevant manner.

The prevention programs designed and implemented by the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) reflect efforts to reach university students through collaborative, educational, and communicative approaches. By combining direct field campaigns, information dissemination through social media, and active involvement of campus communities, the police aim to create an environment that is more aware of the dangers of drug abuse. These efforts still face several challenges, such as limited funding and low student participation in such activities. Nevertheless, the measures taken indicate that prevention efforts continue to progress and are being adapted to the evolving conditions within society and educational environments. A direct approach to students is also carried out through collaboration with student organizations that take the initiative to prevent the spread of drugs within their communities. Several activities involving the police are initiated by the students themselves, such as seminars, training sessions, and group discussions. These activities are usually held upon direct requests from campuses or student organizations, to which POLDA responds by sending speakers to deliver legal materials, preventive education, and real case examples that have been handled.

Through this approach, students are not only recipients of information but also play a role as messengers of prevention among their peers. This collaboration-based approach demonstrates that students can be part of the solution, not merely objects of intervention programs. In addition to focusing on preventive approaches through education, the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) also maximizes programs related to community participation. One example of such activities is involvement in social communities or groups, such as guidance programs in areas vulnerable to drug abuse. Although not limited to university students, these activities sometimes involve young volunteers from higher education institutions. In some cases, POLDA also supports community-based programs aimed at transforming neighborhoods previously known as drug-prone areas into spaces more open to social and educational activities. University students can be empowered through peer-education training or by becoming campus ambassadors for a drug-free environment, exerting influence from within their own communities. These preventive measures are not without limitations, particularly regarding the minimal budget allocated for preventive activities compared to eradication programs. Nevertheless, POLDA continues to schedule prevention activities periodically, aligning them with key moments such as new student admissions or campus orientation periods. Under these constrained conditions, the presence of trained personnel with the capacity to provide education serves as a valuable resource for consistently carrying out these activities. It is also recognized that the success of prevention cannot be achieved solely by the police but requires active involvement from the campus community, student organizations, and the educational institutions themselves.

Collaboration, Approaches, and Challenges in Campus-Based Prevention

Cooperation between the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) and higher education institutions in the region has been established in various forms, both formal, through memoranda of understanding, and informal, through direct communication with campus authorities. One tangible form of this cooperation is POLDA's involvement in seminars or discussion sessions organized by student organizations, such as the Student Executive Board (BEM). On several occasions, campuses have requested POLDA to send representatives as speakers for educational activities on the dangers of narcotics. These activities provide students with the opportunity to engage in direct dialogue with law enforcement officers regarding drug-related issues and to receive more practical explanations. In addition to involvement in student activities, cooperation also takes place through

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the establishment of anti-narcotics task forces or working groups within campuses. These task forces are formed as a follow-up to Presidential Instruction No. 2 of 2020, which encourages the involvement of various community elements in efforts to prevent drug abuse. At the University of Palangka Raya, for example, POLDA Kalteng is involved as part of the legal team within the Campus Anti-Narcotics Task Force. The responsibilities of this team include providing legal guidance, assisting in designing educational programs, and supporting campus activities aimed at raising students' awareness of the risks of narcotics. This involvement demonstrates that the collaboration is not merely ceremonial but focuses on a more substantive role. In terms of approach, POLDA Kalteng begins by establishing communication and coordination with the rectorate or student organization leaders. This communication pattern allows prevention activities to be better planned and aligned with the campus academic calendar. One of the moments often utilized for conducting awareness sessions is during the PKKMB (Campus Life Introduction Program for New Students). During this period, new students tend to be more open to receiving external information, including materials on the dangers of narcotics. By adjusting the schedule and format of these sessions, prevention messages can be delivered more effectively without conflicting with primary academic activities. However, in the implementation of this cooperation, several challenges are still encountered, both from the police side and the campus side. One of the main challenges faced by POLDA Kalteng is budget limitations, especially due to government spending efficiency policies that reduce funds for socialization activities. As a result, activities requiring logistics, such as distributing printed materials, providing equipment, or traveling to campus locations, become difficult to conduct regularly. On the other hand, there are also challenges from the campus side, particularly regarding students' low interest in participating in awareness or narcotics education programs. Most students are more attracted to competitive or entertainment activities than to programs they perceive as formal routines.

Another challenge arises from the limited space for cross-agency collaboration. In some cases, POLDA Kalteng has initiated meetings with other agencies, such as the social services or local government, but the follow-up from these agencies does not always proceed as expected. For example, the plan to transform Kampung Puntun, previously known as a drug-prone area, into a tourist village was initially supported by the city government but later stalled due to a change in officials. Such situations demonstrate that programs that have been initiated can lose direction if not accompanied by consistent coordination from all parties. This limitation also affects the campus environment, especially if prevention activities rely solely on the role of the police without tangible support from external parties. Students themselves do play a role in supporting prevention programs; however, the approach used needs to be adapted to the characteristics of today's youth. Some students demonstrate openness and even participate in peer-education activities, an educational approach where students teach and guide other students. Unfortunately, such initiatives are still not widely found across all campuses. Challenges arise when student groups active in social issues lack strong institutional support, whether from supervising lecturers or campus organizational structures. In fact, their role could serve as a bridge between law enforcement and the student community, delivering messages in a way that is more easily received.

The involvement of students' families in prevention efforts is still very limited. Based on interview findings, parents rarely report or seek help if they find out their child is using drugs. Although there are some examples outside the student context where families actively report and guide their children toward rehabilitation, this has not occurred among university students' families. This makes prevention programs more challenging because early detection, which could ideally be carried out through family involvement, is delayed. In such situations, the campus and law enforcement authorities become the most likely parties to identify cases of abuse, which ideally could have been addressed earlier with family support. Another challenge that arises in the cooperation between the police and educational institutions is the low continuity of programs that have been initiated. Not all campuses have a fixed schedule for narcotics awareness activities, so program implementation tends to be incidental, conducted only when there is a specific request or occasion. For example, narcotics counseling sessions are often held only during PKKMB or in response to incidents involving students. This situation prevents prevention messages from being consistently present in students' daily lives. Some campuses may already have Anti-Narcotics Task Forces, but their activities remain limited and have not yet become part of a year-round campus culture. In fact, the continuity of such activities can enhance outreach and strengthen students' understanding of the risks associated with narcotics. Limited communication is also a factor affecting the effectiveness of cooperation. In some cases, the campus does not actively maintain communication with POLDA Kalteng, even when there is an initiative from law enforcement to get involved. Conversely, there are times when students or internal campus organizations want to organize activities but do not know the procedures or contacts needed to involve the police as partners. The lack of regular and open communication channels prevents many

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potential collaborations from materializing. This issue could be addressed if campuses establish a dedicated unit or appoint a permanent representative to serve as a liaison between the educational institution and the police, ensuring that every initiative can be coordinated directly without having to wait for an incident to occur first. In addition, there is still a perception among some students that narcotics awareness activities are monotonous and uninteresting. This affects the level of student participation in activities organized in collaboration with POLDA. Students tend to be more enthusiastic about interactive activities or those that provide them with space to express their opinions. Therefore, the approach used needs to be more varied, not limited to one-way lectures, but also including discussions, case studies, simulations, or experiential-based training. In this way, students can feel actively involved, rather than merely as listeners. Changing the method of delivery can create new opportunities for existing collaborations to be not only formal but also impactful in shaping students' perspectives on narcotics prevention efforts.

In this regard, the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) applies a strict legal approach to university students involved in the distribution or abuse of narcotics. Students apprehended, whether as users, distributors, or part of a distribution network, are processed in accordance with the provisions of Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics. No special treatment is given based on social status, education, or age. Law enforcement is carried out in the same manner as for other offenders, including arrest, investigation, and the referral of cases to court. This process is intended to provide a clear message that there is no immunity from the law, even for offenders from educated backgrounds. In practice, law enforcement officers conduct preliminary verification by gathering sufficient evidence before making an arrest. If a suspect is proven to be an end-user not involved in distribution, there is a possibility of being directed toward rehabilitation, especially if it is found that the individual did not act as a distributor or courier. However, if the student is also involved in selling or storing large quantities, legal proceedings are carried out with sanctions imposed according to their role. In some cases, students even misuse their status to facilitate distribution access within the campus, which becomes a strong reason for the police to take strict follow-up action.

Handling university students involved in narcotics offenses is not solely oriented toward punishment. In certain situations, particularly for first-time users or those showing an intention to quit, a guidance and rehabilitation approach is considered as an alternative. However, past experiences have shown that some students who have undergone rehabilitation later become involved in similar cases, sometimes with greater levels of involvement. This has led the police to exercise greater caution in determining whether an individual is eligible for rehabilitation or should be processed through the courts. Such decisions are usually made based on the offender's history, the evidence found, and their connection to distribution networks. In several cases handled, students were not only found to be individual users but also part of a broader network. For example, some students were arrested for ordering large quantities of narcotics through interprovincial delivery services. In such cases, investigations are expanded to uncover the network above them, including couriers, suppliers, or other parties involved. This tracing is carried out by examining communication channels, bank accounts, and transaction data collected during the investigation process. The goal is to disrupt the distribution routes of narcotics infiltrating the campus environment, not merely to apprehend street-level offenders. In this way, the legal process becomes more effective in curbing distribution.

In addition to legal proceedings against offenders, POLDA Kalteng also publicizes certain cases involving university students as part of Narcotics Awareness Materials. The most recent session was conducted in July 2025 and delivered by AIPTU Warsito, serving as Ps. Pauranev Subbaganev Bagbinopsnal Ditresnarkoba, POLDA Kalteng. This publication is intended not to shame the offenders but as a warning to other students that involvement with narcotics will have serious consequences for their future. By publicly reporting the arrests, it is hoped that a deterrent effect will arise both for the students involved and for their surrounding environment. This message is expected to reach more students who previously believed that the law would not affect them simply because they are still within the academic setting. The police also acknowledge that the success of law enforcement cannot be separated from the support of the surrounding environment. Unfortunately, the participation of families or the campus in detecting and reporting indications of drug abuse is still limited. In many cases, reports only come after a student has already been caught, rather than when early warning signs appear. This becomes an obstacle to early intervention efforts. Therefore, authorities hope that campuses and families can be more open and proactive in responding to changes in student behavior that may lead to substance abuse. If reports are made earlier, there is a possibility that students can still be handled through rehabilitation channels. Overall, law enforcement against students involved in narcotics is carried out with a balanced approach between justice and rehabilitation efforts. Students are not given special treatment or differentiated from other offenders. However, whenever possible,

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authorities still provide room for rehabilitation, especially for users who have not yet been involved in distribution networks. This process aims to ensure that students do not lose their life direction entirely and still have the opportunity to return to normal academic and social life. Nevertheless, for those clearly involved in distribution or networks, legal proceedings continue as part of the commitment to enforce the law. One of the considerations in taking action against students is their age and legal status. If the student involved is still a minor or a young adult who is psychologically vulnerable, the police may take steps in accordance with child or adolescent protection procedures. However, if the offender meets the legal criteria as an adult, the investigation process is conducted in the same manner as for other suspects. Nevertheless, authorities still take humanitarian aspects into account during law enforcement, particularly by providing opportunities for consultation, guidance, and rehabilitation if the student is deemed more suitable for recovery than harsh punishment.

For students who show no remorse or repeat their offenses, enforcement is carried out without compromise. In some cases, the involvement of students as offenders actually adds complexity to investigations due to the potential networks that exploit their status as intermediaries. The campus environment, which tends to be closed and characterized by dense social interactions, makes narcotics distribution more concealed. In addition, students' use of communication technology accelerates transactions and complicates tracking, especially when they use encrypted applications or online-based transactions. To address this, law enforcement authorities need to collaborate with the campus and digital service providers to identify emerging distribution patterns. This process requires patience and careful attention in integrating information from various sources to unravel the layered distribution network. POLDA Central Kalimantan also stated that law enforcement will not be effective without support from the campus community itself. Many campuses have so far been less actively involved in monitoring their students, especially those already showing signs of behavioral deviation. When violations occur and students are apprehended, campuses tend to respond reactively and do not always provide the data needed during the investigation process. This becomes an obstacle to further handling, as administrative support and internal campus communication can help accelerate legal proceedings while clarifying the offender's background. Therefore, active involvement of educational institutions is needed not only in the prevention stage but also during the legal process to ensure that case handling is not hindered by a lack of information.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the Central Kalimantan Regional Police (POLDA Kalteng) have implemented various preventive efforts to curb narcotics distribution among university students, targeting both the general public and campus environments. Activities such as counseling sessions, socialization programs, direct campaigns, and the use of social media have become the main approaches applied. Although some programs have not been specifically focused on university students, efforts to reach this group have still been carried out through collaboration with student organizations, the involvement of lecturers, and participation in campus activities such as the Student Orientation Program (PKKMB). On the other hand, law enforcement against students involved in narcotics abuse or distribution has been implemented without distinction, while also considering aspects of rehabilitation and guidance whenever possible. However, several challenges remain, including limited budgets, low student participation, a lack of reporting from families, and suboptimal inter-agency coordination. All of these factors pose challenges to creating a campus environment that is more resilient to narcotics influence.

To enhance the effectiveness of narcotics prevention and case handling among university students, it is recommended that the Central Kalimantan Regional Police strengthen programs specifically designed for students and schedule them regularly within the academic calendar. Universities should also take a more active role, not only during formal events such as PKKMB but also through the establishment of support units, the strengthening of Anti-Narcotics Task Forces, and support for peer-education initiatives led by students themselves. In addition, greater synergy is needed among POLDA, the National Narcotics Agency (BNN), local governments, and educational institutions in developing long-term strategies that are not dependent on specific events. Family involvement should also be increased through education and guidance, enabling early detection of students at risk. All parties must work together to foster a campus culture that is aware of the dangers of narcotics and capable of preventing their spread from an early stage.

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